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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF ARGATROBAN IN BULK AND IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid and accurate method was developed for the estimation of Argatroban in bulk and in pharmaceutical dosage form and validated. Here, the solutions of Argatroban were prepared in methanol. The standard solution was scanned in the UV range (200-400 nm) in double beam UV spectrophotometer. It's maximum absorption was found at wavelength 259 nm. Absorbance was measured at 259 nm and calibration curve was plotted as absorbance vs concentration. The method was found to be linear (obeys Beer's law) in the range of 25-125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999 and regression of the curve was found as $y=0.009x+0.052$ with good recovery of 99.37-100.48%. The limit of detection and the limit of quantification were found to be 0.948 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 2.8755 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The ruggedness and robustness were performed. All the parameters of analysis were chosen according to ICH guidelines and were validated statistically using RSD and % RSD with neat chromatograms. All the parameters were found to be satisfactory in accordance with the standard values. The proposed method can be used for routine practice for determination of Argatroban in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations.

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INTRODUCTION

The drug development is a lengthy process involving drug discovery, laboratory testing, animal studies, clinical trials and regulatory registration. To further enhance the effectiveness and safety of the drug product after approval, many regulatory agencies require that the drug be tested for its identity, strength, quality, purity and stability before it is released in the market. UV Visible spectrophotometry involves the measurements of the amount of ultraviolet or visible radiation absorbed by a substance in solution. UV visible spectrophotometry is used for quantitative analysis, for detection of impurities for determination of molecular weight and chemical kinetics.

Argatroban{1-[5-[(aminoiminomethyl)amino]-1-oxo-2-[[1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-3-methyl-8-quinoliny]sulphonyl]amino]pentyl]-4-methyl-2-piperidine carboxylic acid, monohydrate} is used as an anticoagulant for prophylaxis or treatment of thrombosis in patients with heparin induced thrombocytopenia (HIT/HITTS). It is also used in patients with or at risk for heparin induced thrombocytopenia undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). Argatroban is a direct Thrombin inhibitor.^[1] It is a synthetic nonpeptide compound which binds reversibly to the catalytic site of thrombin but not to the substrate recognition site. As such, it produces a rapid and short lasting antithrombin action.^[2] It does not require the co-factor antithrombin III for antithrombotic activity. It exerts its effects by inhibiting thrombin catalysed or induced reactions, including fibrin formation; activation of coagulation factors V, VIII, and XIII; activation of protein C; and platelet aggregation. Argatroban is highly selective for thrombin with an inhibitory constant (K_i) of 0.004 μM . It is approved for use in India by the Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation. The Argatroban is available in injection form (50 mg in 50 ml single use vial). Its molecular formula is $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the molecular weight is 526.66.^[3] Due to its selective inhibitory mechanism, Argatroban blocks both circulating and clot-bound thrombin. The elimination half-life of Argatroban is (52 \pm 16 minutes) which is short enough to ensure a rapid restoration of haemostasis upon cessation of treatment. Argatroban produces a predictable dose response, and its anticoagulant actions can be monitored easily through the routine coagulation tests activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) and activated clotting time (ACT).

Fig. 1: Structure of Argatroban.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Apparatus and instruments:

- A double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Systronics model 2210),
- Electronic balance AY220 (Shimadzu, Japan)
- Ultra sonicator (Microclean-103)
- Glass beakers and volumetric flasks of appropriate volume (Borosil glassworks Ltd.)

Reagents and material:

- Argatroban (Gift sample from Aurobindo Pharmaceutical limited, Hyderabad)
- Methanol LR
- Injection of 250mg/2.5mL was purchased from local pharmacy in solapur under commercially available brand name ARGANAT (NATCO).

Methods

Preliminary analysis of drug

a) **Description:** The sample of Argatroban was observed for its color and texture.

b) **Solubility:** The sample of Argatroban was taken in test tubes and observed for solubility in various solvents like methanol, acetonitrile and water.

c) **Identification Test:** 1 mg of Argatroban was kept on selenide crystal and was scanned in the region of 4000-400 cm^{-1} for its IR spectrum.

d) **Melting point:** Capillary filled with Argatroban was kept in melting point apparatus and melting point was determined and compared with the reference.

UV spectrophotometric method for Argatroban

- Mode : Spectrum
- Measuring mode : Absorbance
- Scanning speed : Medium
- Slit width : 2nm
- Wavelength range : 200-400nm
- Absorbance scale : 0.00A-2A

Selection of solvent

Solubility of Argatroban was checked in various solvents like methanol, acetonitrile and water.

Preparation of stock solutions

A primary stock solution (1000 µg/ml) was prepared in methanol. The standard stock solution was prepared by dilution of the primary stock solution with methanol to obtain working standard of concentration 500µg/ml.

Determination of Absorption Maxima (λ_{max})

Argatroban solution was scanned in the range of 200-400 nm to determine wavelength at which it absorbs maximum.

Calibration curve for Argatroban

This series consisted of five concentrations of standard Argatroban solution ranging from 25-125 µg/ml. The solutions were prepared by pipetting out standard Argatroban stock solution (0.5ml, 1ml, 1.5ml, 2ml, 2.5ml) was transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted up to mark with methanol. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 259 nm against methanol as a blank. Calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance (y-axis) versus respective concentration (x-axis) of Argatroban.

Quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical injection dosage form

0.1ml from injection vial of strength 250mg/2.5ml i.e. 100mg/ml was taken and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made upto 10 ml to make 1000 µg/ml solution. This solution was sonicated and filtered using 0.45 µ filter. 5ml of this solution was taken and diluted to 10 ml with methanol to make 500 µg/ml solution. Again 0.5 ml of this solution was diluted to 10 ml to make 25 µg/ml solution and the absorbance was measured at 259 nm.

Validation of proposed method⁹:

The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines for the following parameters.

Linearity

25, 50, 75, 100, 125 µg/ml concentration solutions of Argatroban were prepared by transferring 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5ml of standard solution into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and making the volume upto 10 ml. Then absorption of these solutions were recorded and the graph was plotted of absorbance against concentration. The correlation coefficient of least square linear regression of Argatroban was calculated.

The linearity response was determined by analyzing 6 independent levels of calibration curve in the range of 25-125 µg/ml (n=6) for Argatroban.

Range

The range of the analytical method was decided from the interval between the upper and lower level of analyte obtained from the calibration curve.

Precision

The precision expresses the degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple sampling of a homogenous sample. It was determined in terms of repeatability and intermediate precision (intraday and interday precisions).

Repeatability

Repeatability was determined by analysing six samples of same concentration of drug (75µg/ml) by recording their absorbance.

Intermediate precision (Intraday and interday precision)

Intraday precision was determined by analysing 75µg/ml concentration solutions for 3 times a day.

Interday precision was determined similarly but the analysis was carried out for two consecutive days.

Robustness

The robustness of developed method is its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters. Here, the wavelength of the analysis was deliberately varied and absorbance was noted. The effect of detection wavelength was studied at ± 5 nm was studied.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness is defined as the degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same sample under a variety of conditions. It was determined by performing analysis by two different analysts and recording absorbances. The results were indicated as % RSD.

Limit of detection (LOD)

It is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated under the stated experimental conditions. It was determined based on the standard deviation of absorbances of same concentration (75 μ g/ml) prepared six times. LOD was calculated from the formula as follows:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 (\text{SD/S})$$

Where SD = standard deviation; s = slope of the curve.

Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

It is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated experimental conditions. It was determined based on the standard deviation of absorbances of same concentration (75 μ g/ml) prepared six times. LOQ was calculated from the formula as follows:

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 (\text{SD/S})$$

Where SD = standard deviation; s = slope of the curve.

Accuracy

It is defined as the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value.

It was determined by calculating the recovery of Argatroban by standard addition method. The known amount of Argatroban was added to the preanalysed sample at three different concentration levels i.e. 80%, 100%, 120% of assay concentration. Each solution was taken and diluted with methanol upto 10ml in volumetric flask and scanned between 200nm to 400 nm against methanol as a blank. The amount of Argatroban was calculated at each level and % recoveries were computed.

0.5 ml of injection solution was transferred to four different 10 ml volumetric flask (labelled as 0, 80%, 100%, 120%) separately and 0, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 ml of 500 μ g/ml standard solution was added respectively and the volume was made upto the mark with methanol. Absorbances were noted for these solutions. Standard deviation and % RSD were calculated. Accuracy was reported as % recovery, which was calculated from the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{\text{Observed value}}{\text{True value}} \times 100$$

RESULTS

Preliminary analysis of drug

a) **Description:** The sample of Argatroban was white in colour.

b) **Solubility:** Argatroban was found to be soluble in methanol. So, methanol was used as a solvent.

c) **Identification Test:** 1 mg of Argatroban was kept on selenide crystal and was scanned in the region of 4000-400 cm^{-1} for its IR spectrum.

Fig.2. IR Spectrum of Argatroban.

Table 1: Functional groups detection by IR spectrum.

Wave no.	Functional groups
3430.68	-NH ₂
1685.83	-C=O
2948.58	-C-H

d) Melting point: Melting point of Argatroban was found to be 218⁰C.

Selection of solvent

It was found that Argatroban is soluble in methanol. In the present investigation, methanol was used as a solvent.

Determination of Absorption Maxima (λ_{max})

λ_{max} of the drug was found to be 259 nm.

Calibration curve for Argatroban

The calibration curve showed linearity in the range of 25-125 μ g/ml with a correlation coefficient of 0.999 and regression equation as $y = 0.009x + 0.052$.

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Argatroban.

Quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical injection dosage form

Table 2: Determination of Argatroban in injection dosage form.

Injection form	Labelled claim	Amount taken	Amount found	Assay %
ARGANAT	250mg	50 μ g	50.35 μ g	100.7

Determination of Wavelength of Maximum absorption

The wavelength of maximum absorption was found to be 259 nm.

Figure 4: Wavelength of maximum absorption of Argatroban.

Validated parameters

Linearity

The linearity was found to be ranging from 25 – 125 µg/ml and the regression equation was found by $y=0.009x+0.052$ ($r^2 = 0.999$).

Table 3: Linearity.

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
1	25	0.288
2	50	0.539
3	75	0.790
4	100	1.034
5	125	1.255

Figure 5: Linearity graph of Argatroban.

Precision

Intraday precision

Table 4: Intraday morning precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.79		
2	75	0.784		
3	75	0.787		
4	75	0.784		
5	75	0.783		
6	75	0.785	0.002588	0.3295
		$\hat{y}=0.7855$		

Table 5: Intraday afternoon precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.801		
2	75	0.800		
3	75	0.799		
4	75	0.796		
5	75	0.794		
6	75	0.795	0.002881	0.3612
		$\hat{y}=0.7975$		

Table 6: Intraday evening precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.800		
2	75	0.802		
3	75	0.806		
4	75	0.803		
5	75	0.806		
6	75	0.808	0.002994	0.3723
		$\hat{y}=0.8041$		

Interday precision

Table 7: Interday morning precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.805		
2	75	0.810		
3	75	0.808		
4	75	0.807		
5	75	0.810		
6	75	0.810	0.002066	0.2555
		$\hat{y}=0.8083$		

Table 8: Interday afternoon precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.819		
2	75	0.819		
3	75	0.821		
4	75	0.817		
5	75	0.819		
6	75	0.824	0.002401	0.2928
		$\hat{y}=0.8198$		

Table 9: Interday evening precision.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.825		
2	75	0.826		
3	75	0.828		
4	75	0.824		
5	75	0.823		
6	75	0.824	0.001789	0.2168
		$\hat{y}=0.825$		

Repeatability**Table 10: Repeatability study.**

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	75	0.79		
2	75	0.784		
3	75	0.787		
4	75	0.784		
5	75	0.783		
6	75	0.785	0.002588	0.3295
		$\hat{y}=0.7855$		

Range : 25 – 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (from calibration curve)

Limit of Detection (LOD)

Table 11: Limit of detection.

LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.9489
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Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

Table 12: Limit of Quantitation.

LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.8755
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Robustness**Table 13: Robustness study.**

Sr. No.	Wavelength(nm)	Absorbance	SD	%RSD
1	258	0.769		
2	259	0.785		
3	260	0.783	0.008718	1.119
		$\hat{y}=0.779$		

Ruggedness

Analyst – 1

Table 14: Ruggedness (Analyst-1).

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	Statistical analysis
75	0.790	
75	0.784	Mean = 0.7855
75	0.787	SD = 0.002555
75	0.784	%RSD = 0.3295
75	0.783	
75	0.785	

Analyst – 2

Table 15: Ruggedness (Analyst-2).

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	Statistical analysis
75	0.792	
75	0.788	Mean = 0.788833
75	0.787	SD = 0.002137
75	0.791	%RSD = 0.270907
75	0.787	
75	0.788	

Accuracy

Table 16: Accuracy.

Sr. No.	Level of % Recovery	Amount of injection sample (ml)	Amount of standard drug added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount added (μg)	Amount found (μg)	% Recovery
1	0	0.5	0	0	0	
2	80	0.5	0.4	20	20.05	100.25
3	100	0.5	0.5	25	25.12	100.48
4	120	0.5	0.6	30	30.19	99.37

DISCUSSION

Preliminary analysis

Preliminary analysis of Argatroban (description, solubility, identification test, selection of wavelength and melting point) were performed.

UV spectrophotometry

Since Argatroban is UV absorbing drug, UV spectrophotometric method has been applied for its quantitative determination. The drug was found to be soluble in methanol. So all the solutions for analysis were prepared in methanol. The wavelength of maximum absorption was found to be 259 nm by scanning in UV range (200 – 400 nm). The calibration curve was plotted and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999. The range where it obeys the Beer's law was found to be 25-125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.9489 and 2.8755 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The method was validated with respect to all the parameters and hence the method can be applied for routine analysis of the drug.

Summary & Conclusion

Summary of UV spectrophotometric method of Argatroban

Table 17: Summary.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Values
1	Wavelength of maximum absorption	259 nm
2	Standard regression equation	$y = 0.009x + 0.052$
3	Correlation coefficient	0.999
4	Range	25 – 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
5	Precision (%RSD of repeatability)	0.3295 %
6	Robustness (%RSD)	1.119%
7	Ruggedness (%RSD)	0.3295 and 0.270907
8	LOD	0.9489 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
9	LOQ	2.8755 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
10	Accuracy (%Recovery)	99.37-100.48 %

CONCLUSION

A simple, rapid and accurate UV spectrophotometric method was developed and validated according to ICH guidelines. All parameters were found to be within standard range. This method can be applied to routine analysis of Argatroban in bulk and in pharmaceutical dosage form. In this proposed method, cost effective reagents were used as well as the method was found to be accurate, simple and rapid which are its valuable benefits.

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